

**ПЕДАГОГИК ВА
ПСИХОЛОГИК
ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР**

ЯНВАРЬ, 2023

1-СОН

**PEDAGOGICAL AND
PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDIES**

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ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ**

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НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ
НОМЕР-1**

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ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР
ИЛМИЙ-АМАЛИЙ ЖУРНАЛ
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Мазкур фанлараро илмий-амалий журнал Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Администрацияси ҳузуридаги Ахборот ва оммавий коммуникациялар агентлиги томонидан 2022 йил 22 декабрь куни № 054834-сонли гувоҳнома билан оммавий ахборот воситаси сифатида давлат рўйхатидан ўтказилган.

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Таҳририят манзили: <https://imfaktor.uz>, 100152, Тошкент шаҳри, Учтепа тумани, “Ватан” МФЙ, Чилонзор 24-мавзеси, 2/27-уй.

Телефон номер: +99894-410 11 55, **E-mail:** tahririyat@imfaktor.uz

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KARSHIBOEVA Aziza

ABDURAKHMONOVA Karima

Students of School management Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

ALIMOVA Kunduz

Teacher of School management Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

THE IMPACT OF DECENTRALIZATION OF EDUCATION ON THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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ANNOTATION

This article discusses the content of the decentralization of the education system, its economic and social aspects, and the future prospects of the education system. In addition, in this article, the positive and negative aspects of decentralization to the educational system, as well as the work and theoretical foundations of scientists about the content of decentralization are also mentioned. The article contains information about decentralization processes in Uzbekistan and foreign countries.

Key words: decentralization, standard, DTS, competition, competitiveness, innovation, classification, financing, administrative management, function.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada ta'lim tizimini markazsizlashtirishning mazmuni, uning iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy jihatlari, ta'lim tizimining kelajakdagi istiqbollari muhokama qilinadi. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqolada ta'lim tizimiga markazsizlashtirishning ijobiy va salbiy tomonlari, shuningdek, markazsizlashtirishning mazmuni haqidagi olimlarning faoliyati va nazariy asoslari ham aytib o'tilgan. Maqolada O'zbekiston va xorijiy mamlakatlardagi markazsizlashtirish jarayonlari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: markazsizlashtirish, standart, DTS, raqobat, raqobatbardoshlik, innovatsiya, tasniflash, moliyalashtirish, ma'muriy boshqaruv, funktsiya.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматривается содержание децентрализации системы образования, ее экономические и социальные аспекты, а также дальнейшие перспективы системы образования. Кроме того, в этой статье также упоминаются положительные и отрицательные стороны децентрализации системы образования, а также работы и теоретические основы ученых о содержании децентрализации. В статье содержится информация о процессах децентрализации в Узбекистане и зарубежных странах.

Ключевые слова: децентрализация, стандарт, ДТС, конкуренция, конкурентоспособность, инновации, классификация, финансирование, административное управление, функция.

***Education does not create a person, but allows him to create himself.
Mauris Debesse***

More than a thousand and a thousand changes have been taking place since the time when humanity appeared, the primitive community system, until now. We can take as an example the measures related to self-development, from inventing and buying new products and improving social living conditions. In a word, the basis of all this is **education**.

Education has such a general and systematic nature that through it we can understand the whole existence that surrounds us, even our own identity. Sometimes knowingly or unknowingly, we are considered to be the participants of this huge system, who are forced or negatively affected by it.

The educational system is a system that manages the types of education, standards and all their requirements and powers in the state. Of course, the attention given to education will affect the improvement of all aspects of this country or society. All fields begin and end in education. Because of this, systematization and integration of education is very important. To what extent will it benefit the education system to not over centralize the education system, to reduce state intervention even partially, and to increase the independence of this sector?

It is not secret that we are currently in an area of rapid information and intense competition. In this process, how effective is the decentralization of the state sector for the benefit of the state?

Where the flow of information is constantly updated day by day, encourages everyone to take action.

The state should not be afraid of decentralization. Because where there is freedom and independence, there will be innovation and development [2, P.85]. Staying abreast of the times, strengthening competitiveness and striving for a high rating, progress wherever there is independence. Here, education is no exception.

Decentralization is gradually spreading throughout the world. We can see the result of this in the example of recent changes and political strategies in developed countries.

Decentralization allows teachers to consider the local context and address diversity among the students they teach. Therefore, the decentralization of management in education is strongly related to the Finnish Way of interpreting the professional competence and the status of teachers in Finnish society [4, P.97].

Decentralization of education can be implemented in social, economic and administrative aspects. The state maintains control over the quality of education and the requirements and standards of education and transfers administrative management, financing of educational institutions, promotion of innovations and wide implementation of functions to full-blooded educational institutions and organizations need a gift. I think it would be better to revise the educational requirements and standards to conform to the international education classification standard adopted by UNESCO. However, this international standard clearly defines what the standards for all stages of education should be, and how high results can be achieved. According the world experience, national education standards should be based not on the experience of the state, which has its own social, economic and cultural characteristics, but on the standards of the international education classification. Then the possibility of training highly qualified, competitive personnel who can meet the requirements of world standards will increase the above-mentioned idea is once again changing the view of education.

It is well known that decentralization started throughout republic, initially with self-financing. According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers “On gradual transfer of higher education institutions to the self-financing system” (No. 967, 03.12.2019) from January 1, 2020, 10 higher education institutions switched to the self-financing system as a trial. This allows higher education institutions to determine the amount and terms of payment for student studying on the basis of a payment contract.

At this point, we may have a questions:

Won't the activities of higher education institution that have gained independence due to decentralization deviate in a negative direction?

How does the activity of authorized higher education institutions affect the education system?

We can answer these questions through the laws and regulations set by the state, that is, through the State Educational Standard, Laws “On Education” to prevent such negative process can be obtained. Decentralization does not depend on one higher education institution from another higher education institution in terms of curricula and education programs, and self-financing benefits the state budget and helps to improve the state's economic situation. In addition to this, the population itself is the main factor in determining the rating of higher education in the context of widespread decentralization. For example, public opinion increases the perspective and competitiveness of a higher educational, and on the contrary, an educational institution that has a negative attitude may be criticized and later completely end its work. This allows to increase not only the quantity, but also the quality.

In this regard, it is appropriate to recall the following words of the teacher of Russian pedagogues, Konstantin Dmitrievich Ushinsky: “The independence of the student head is the only solid foundation of any effective education” [7, P.2].

If we look at developed countries, we can be sure that a lot of effort and investment will be made in the social sphere, education and health care, economy and other important areas. Every underdeveloped country has not paid attention to the field of education, and there is no developed country without education. The reform and development of the education sector is the most important and one of the first areas to pay attention to in order to enter the ranks of the developed first world countries from a developing country.

Nowadays, we can find centralized and decentralized educational institutions. But recently, we are witnessing the transfer of centralized educational organizations from the state to a decentralized system.

Despite the fact that this process has become popular mainly in the first world countries, we see that this process has recently been organized in our country, the Republic of Uzbekistan. And the main goal of this process is to develop the state, i.e., leaving the state, this educational organization is mainly considered as higher education, self-management, financing, and creating a quality and clean educational environment through pure competition. We are witnessing through private educational organizations.

If we compare some important differences between public and private higher education institutions in our country, this is a big difference in the grant program allocated to their highly educated students, and we can see that this has two different effects on students' studies at the time. We will go out. If we look at the statistics, there are currently more than 100 public higher education institutions, and each of them has students studying on the basis of payment grants [3, P.37].

McGinn and Welsh argue that the need to decentralize education stems from new economic and technological conditions in the world [6, P.21].

First, the political debate of the 1970s and 1980s shifted economic policy from Keynesian-inspired economic thought to market-oriented economic policy. A market-oriented economy was seen as the best way to allocate resources in society; The market, not the central government, should decide how resources should be allocated. This market-oriented approach has also influenced education; it was no longer apparent that a centralized educational system was the most effective; rather, an education system that distributed its resources based on market principles could be more efficient than a centralized system [5, P.671]. The collapse of the communist bloc in Eastern Europe, based on a centralized government system, also promoted organizational reforms toward a market-oriented government organization.

Second, economic and financial globalization has weakened the central government, and increased ties between different communities, rather than between different national governments, have empowered local groups to gain more influence in society. With increasing enrollment rates, centralized education systems have grown in size.

The main goals and tasks of foreign scientists in the formation of the decentralization process. methods and experiences, paying close attention to the levels of political, social and economic development of each region they emphasized that the reforms in this field would solve their destiny. The issues of decentralization of state authorities were discussed by the world's largest institutions, World Bank, ADB, Tacis and others. In general, when summarizing the world experience, attention is paid to the fact that the process of decentralization consists of different forms

Theoretical aspects of the democratization or decentralization of the management of state and local authorities in Uzbekistan political scientist and jurist A. Oripov, B. Joraev, A. Begmatov, S. Doliev, R. Madirimov, O.T. Khusanov, M. Kyrgyzboev, R.Z It was studied by such scientists as Jumaev, Sh. Jalilov, F. Musaev, M. Qoriyeva, F. Jurakulov [1, P.42,43].

Within the framework of the general principles of decentralization, it can be observed that in each country there are specific reasons, forms and results of decentralization, and the nature, genesis and development of mutual relations between the central and local authorities in each country, and the unique aspects of the basic social cadres manifest themselves. Therefore, in this chapter, problems such as the theory of decentralization of state executive power bodies, its development, various interpretations, as well as the experience of decentralization of the system of executive power bodies of developed countries are studied from a scientific point of view.

In short, decentralization represents the presence of elected power independent of the administrative power of the state at the local level, in which the local government performs its powers and obligations within the framework of the law, and takes the status of self-government under the control of the state. In this sense, decentralization cannot be separated from local self-government and democratic principles as a separate reality.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Karimov I.A. Uzbekistan is aspiring to the 21st century. -Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2000, pp. 41-245.
2. Ainscow, M., Dyson, A., Hopwood, L. and Thomson, S., 2016. Primary Schools Responding to Diversity: barriers and possibilities. CPRT Research Survey 8. York: Cambridge Primary Review Trust.P.187.
3. Androniceanu, A. and Ristea, B., 2014. 'Decision Making Process in the Decentralized Educational System' Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences, 149, 37–42.
4. Hargreaves, A. and Ainscow, M., 2015. 'The top and bottom of leadership and change' Phi Delta Kappan, November 2015, 97.
5. Urbanovič, J. and Patapas, A., 2012. 'Decentralisation Reforms of Education Management: Theoretical and Practical Issues' Viešoji Politika ir Administravimas/Public Policy and Administration, 2012, 11 (4), 659–671.
6. Love Edquist Tutor: Prof. Benny Hjern . Decentralization of Educational Management in Vietnam.June 2005.P-95.
7. Statements in prose about the importance of quality education. Quotes about studying., 2020. P.7.